

HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AND ITS COMPONENTS IN PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract. *In this article, the author outlined all the components of a healthy lifestyle in philosophy. A healthy lifestyle is an individual system of human behavior that provides him with physical, mental and social well-being in the real environment (natural, man-made and social) and active longevity.*

Key words: *anthropology, concept, theories, philosophy, Arab Muslim philosophy.*

ЗДОРОВЫЙ ОБРАЗ ЖИЗНИ И ЕГО СОСТАВЛЯЮЩИЕ В ФИЛОСОФИИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор изложил все составляющие здорового образа жизни в философии. Здоровый образ жизни — это индивидуальная система поведения человека, обеспечивающая ему физическое, душевное и социальное благополучие в реальной окружающей среде (природной, техногенной и социальной) и активное долголетие.*

Ключевые слова: *антропология, концепция, теории, философия, арабо мусульманская философия.*

A person's entire life passes in the mode of time distribution, partly forced, associated with socially necessary activities, partly according to an individual plan. So, for example, a student's daily routine is determined by the curriculum of classes at an educational institution, a military serviceman's routine is determined by the daily routine approved by the commander of a military unit, a working person's routine is determined by the beginning and end of the working day.

Thus, a regime is an established routine for a person's life, which includes work, nutrition, rest and sleep.

The main component of a person's lifestyle is his work, which represents the purposeful activity of a person aimed at creating material and spiritual values.

A person's lifestyle must be subordinated, first of all, to his effective work activity. A working person lives in a certain rhythm: he must get up at a certain time, perform his duties, eat, rest and sleep. And this is not surprising - all processes in nature are subject to a strict rhythm to one degree or another: the seasons alternate, night follows day, day again comes to replace night.

Rhythmic activity is one of the basic laws of life and one of the foundations of any work.

A rational combination of elements of a lifestyle ensures more productive human work and a high level of health. The whole organism as a whole participates in human labor activity. The work rhythm sets the physiological rhythm: at certain hours the body experiences stress, as a result of which metabolism increases, blood circulation increases, and then a feeling of fatigue appears; at other hours and days, when the load is reduced, rest comes after fatigue, strength and energy are restored. Proper alternation of load and rest is the basis for high human performance.

The most effective way to restore performance is active rest, which allows you to rationally use your free time. Alternating types of work, a harmonious combination of mental and physical labor, and physical education ensure effective restoration of strength and energy. A person needs

to rest daily, weekly on weekends, annually during the next vacation, using free time to strengthen physical and spiritual health.

Physical culture has always occupied a leading place in preparing a person for active, fruitful life. It can successfully solve the problem of disturbed balance between the strength of emotional stimuli and the realization of the physical needs of the body. This is the right path to strengthening spiritual and physical health.

Physical education has an important impact on a person's ability to adapt to sudden and severe functional fluctuations. A person has a total of 600 muscles, and this powerful motor apparatus requires constant training and exercise. Muscular movements create a huge flow of nerve impulses sent to the brain, maintain the normal tone of the nerve centers, charge them with energy, and relieve emotional overload. In addition, people who constantly engage in physical activity look more attractive in appearance. Physical education is the best measure to prevent alcohol consumption, smoking and drug addiction.

Training gives a person self-confidence. People who regularly engage in physical activity are less susceptible to stress, they cope better with worry, anxiety, depression, anger and fear. They are not only able to relax more easily, but also know how to relieve emotional stress with the help of certain exercises. Physically trained people are better able to resist illness, it is easier for them to fall asleep on time, they sleep more soundly, and they need less time to sleep. Some physiologists believe that every hour of physical activity extends a person's life by two to three hours.

Daily morning exercises are a mandatory minimum of physical activity for the day. It is necessary to make it the same habit as washing your face in the morning.

Hardening is an increase in the body's resistance to the adverse effects of a number of environmental factors (for example, low or high temperature) through systematic exposure to these factors.

Modern homes, clothing, transport, etc. reduce the impact on the human body of atmospheric influences, such as temperature, humidity, and sunlight. Reducing such influences on our body reduces its resistance to environmental factors. Hardening is a powerful healing tool. With its help, you can avoid many diseases and maintain your ability to work and enjoy life for a long time. The role of hardening is especially important in the prevention of colds. Hardening procedures reduce their number by 2-4 times, and in some cases help to get rid of colds altogether. Hardening has a general strengthening effect on the body, increases the tone of the central nervous system, improves blood circulation, and normalizes metabolism.

The main conditions that must be met when hardening the body are the systematic use of hardening procedures and a gradual increase in the force of influence. We must remember that 2-3 months after the cessation of hardening, the previously achieved level of resistance of the body begins to decline.

The most common form of hardening is the use of fresh cool air. Long walks, hiking trips, and sleeping indoors with an open window are good for this in the warm season.

At home, it is useful to walk on the floor barefoot, and for the first time during! minutes, then increase the duration by 1 minute every week. In the cold season, walking is well complemented by skiing, skating, and slow hardening jogging in lightweight clothing. Doing

morning exercises outdoors or in a thoroughly ventilated room also helps increase resistance to low temperatures.

A stronger hardening factor is water. In addition to temperature, water has a mechanical effect on the skin, which is a kind of massage that improves blood circulation.

Hardening can be carried out in the form of rubbing or dousing with water. Hardening with water begins at a temperature not lower than 33-35 degrees and then every 6-7 days the water is cooled by one degree. If no changes occur in the body, the water temperature can be brought to tap temperature (10-12 degrees).

Swimming in open water has a great hardening effect. In this case, irritation by water is combined with exposure to air. When swimming, the warming of the body is facilitated by increased muscle work during swimming. At first, the duration of bathing is 4-5 minutes, gradually increasing it to 15-20 minutes. When you swim for too long or in very cold water, your increased metabolism is unable to replenish the heat loss and the body becomes hypothermic. As a result, instead of hardening, a person harms his health.

One of the hardening factors is solar radiation. It causes vasodilation, enhances the activity of hematopoietic organs, and promotes the formation of vitamin D in the body. This is especially important for preventing rickets in children.

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